

CONCEPTUAL MODEL OF AN AUTOMATED CONTROL SYSTEM FOR TROUBLESHOOTING IN RAILWAY TRANSPORT

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Abstract. The article discusses the conceptual model of automated information systems of the automated system of commercial monthly inspection (AS CMI) for the railway transport system. The principles of the model are given, the goals of creating systems are defined, the scheme of user interaction with the AS of the CMI is considered. The automated system of commercial monthly inspection and data analysis allows to improve the quality of monthly inspections, the level of control and responsibility of managers.

Keywords: automated system, AS CMI, model, modeling, analysis, devices, diagram, algorithm, accounting and control, structure, database.

A conceptual model is a model created in a formal language in the form of a mathematical formula, in the verbal or graphical form of elements of the simulated system (enterprise), connections between elements of processes occurring in the original, under the influence of the external environment.

The construction of a conceptual model, in our opinion, is the most important stage in the general scheme of the algorithm for developing a simulation model of an industrial enterprise due to its considerable labor intensity. It includes: definition and description of the main components of the internal structure of the system, description of the structure of processes in the system and their corresponding flow configurations, definition of strategies and rules for managing processes in the system, the composition of the source data and output indicators of the model, formalization of the model [1].

The construction of a conceptual model begins with the analysis of the initial data about the system and service processes and assumes:

- definition and formulation of object modeling goals, identification and description of tasks solved by modeling;
- identification of the main parts of the object and, accordingly, the object model, their purpose, functioning features, including structural parts (subsystems, components, elements such as nodes, devices, etc.) and processes (functions) occurring in them;
- description of the law of the functioning of the model, known functional, cause-and-effect relationships;

The AS CMI system is aimed at improving the efficiency of commission inspections of stations, strengthening control over the timely and qualitative elimination of identified malfunctions at stations, increasing the overall level of the current maintenance of technical devices of stations, strengthening the interaction of involved services in these matters [2]. When developing the conceptual model, the following tasks were set:

- description of the subject area;
- designing a conceptual data model;
- business process modeling;
- designing the physical structure of the database.

The solution of these tasks provides for the creation of a database of accounting and control of CMI at stations.

The subject area of an information system is a material system or a system that characterizes the elements of the material world, information about which is stored and processed. The subject area is considered as a set of real objects and connections between them.

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The main goals of creating an automated system:

- automation of document flow in the process of organizing and conducting a monthly commission inspection of the station;
- systematization of data on identified malfunctions of technical devices of the station for the purpose of processing for the analysis of the state of train safety;
- increasing the level of control over the timeliness and quality of elimination of identified malfunctions of the station's technical devices;
- improving the quality of the monthly commission inspection of the station;
- increasing the level of responsibility of station managers and managers of road enterprises for the condition of the station's technical devices.

To describe the results of the monthly commission inspection of the station, the following basic information is entered into the system database:

- date, time and area of the station inspection;
- the composition of the inspection commission;
- fault detection location;
- faulty technical device of the station;
- type of technical device malfunction;
- responsible for the elimination of the identified malfunction;
- the actual period of troubleshooting[3].

The IDEF0 notation (Integration Definition for Function Modeling) was developed based on the SADT structural analysis and design methodology, approved as a US standard and successfully used in many projects related to the description of enterprise activities. IDEF0 can be used to model a wide class of systems. For new systems, the use of IDEF0 is aimed at defining requirements and specifying functions for the subsequent development of a system that meets the requirements and implements the selected functions. For existing systems, IDEF0 can be used to analyze the functions performed by the system and display the

mechanisms by which these functions are performed. The result of applying IDEF0 to some system is a model of this system consisting of a hierarchically ordered set of diagrams, documentation text and dictionaries linked to each other by cross-references.

Fig.1. Context diagram

A context diagram is a model representing a system as a set of hierarchical actions in which each action transforms some object or set of objects. The highest action of the hierarchy is called the context action — this is the highest level that directly describes the system. The levels below are called generated decompositions and represent subprocesses of the parent action.

We decompose the context diagram into 4 functional blocks (Fig.2):

- Formation and directions to the corresponding departments of the statement according to the identified criteria
- Registration of inspection results in the AS CMI system
- Troubleshooting and fixing notification

• Accounting and control

Fig. 2. Diagram IDEF0

Next, we will model the system using data flow diagrams (DFD).

We decompose the functional block "Accounting and control" into five more actions (Fig.3):

- Conducting a CMI at the station
- Fault detection
- Entering the results into the AS of the CMI
- Accounting and control

Fig.3. DFD chart "Accounting and control" [4]

The construction of an information model of the subject area involves the allocation of entities, their attributes and primary keys, identification of relationships between entities. A generally accepted type of graphical representation of a relational

data model is an ER diagram, in which entities are represented by rectangles connected by links. Such a graphical representation facilitates the perception of the database structure in comparison with a textual description.

The main advantages of ER models:

- visibility;
- models allow you to design databases with a large number of objects and attributes.

ER models are implemented in many computer-aided database design systems.

IDEF1X describes a collection/set of instances similar in properties, but uniquely distinguished from each other by one or more features. Each instance is an implementation of an entity, i.e. an entity in IDEF1X describes a specific set of instances of the real world, unlike an entity in IDEF1, which is an abstract set of information mappings of the real world. An entity is a set of instances of real or abstract objects (a person, a place, a thing, an event, a state, a concept, an idea, an object, etc.) that have common attributes or characteristics, and about which information needs to be stored.

Basic elements of ER models:

- objects (entities);
- attributes of objects;
- relationships between objects

There are two levels of representation and modeling - logical and physical. The logical level means a direct display of facts from real life. For example, people, desks, departments, computers are real objects. They are named in natural language, with any word separators (spaces, commas, etc.). At the logical level, the use of a specific DBMS is not considered, data types are not defined (for example, integer or real number) and indexes for tables are not defined.

Diagram of the level of entities and attributes, in the IDEF1X notation of the logical level of the model:

The physical layer of the model consists of the target DBMS, object names and data types, indexes. ERD is a diagram in the IDEF1X notation of the physical layer.

All tables are created based on an information model, and each entity will have a separate table. The key fields will correspond to the primary keys of the entities.

The data schema is a graphical image of the database. It is used by various Access objects to define relationships between multiple tables. For example, when creating a form containing data from several interconnected tables, the data schema provides automatic consistent access to the fields of these tables. It also ensures the integrity of interrelated data when correcting tables.

The "one-to-many" type of communication was used in our database. The one-to-many relationship is the most commonly used type of relationship between tables. With respect to "one-to-many", each record in Table A can correspond to several records in Table B, but a record in table B cannot have more than one corresponding record in Table A. The database is implemented in the form of eight interconnected tables in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Data schema

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